

Walnut Production Within Agroforestry Systems

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Test field with leek and walnut tree rows, Inagro

Agroforestry combines woody perennials or shrubs with the cultivation of crops or livestock. Walnut trees are particularly well-suited to this system due to their deep roots, low growth, open canopy, and late leaf development. These characteristics reduce competition for sunlight and water, benefiting the surrounding crops. While walnut trees have been present in Belgium for centuries, most of the walnuts consumed here are imported. With the growing demand for locally and sustainably produced products, the combination of agroforestry and walnut trees presents an interesting opportunity to achieve both ecological and economic benefits. The choice of crops plays a crucial role in the success of agroforestry. Vegetables such as summer, winter, or autumn leeks compete less with trees for light and water, while issues like leaf fall are minimized. Moreover, leaf fall provides advantages by adding organic material to the soil, increasing carbon storage. When tree rows are combined with grasses and herbs, they create habitats for natural pest control, contributing to a healthier and more resilient ecosystem. In this way, agroforestry enhances not only agricultural production but also the biodiversity of the land. Walnut trees thrive best in well-drained, airy, and deep soils, avoiding areas with high groundwater levels. The ultimate purpose of the planting—whether for nut production or timber—determines the choice of tree varieties and pruning methods. To achieve optimal yields, selecting suitable varieties that ensure effective pollination is essential. By carefully aligning these factors, farmers can not only improve the quality of their final products but also contribute to a more sustainable agricultural system. Agroforestry with walnut trees thus offers a versatile and forward-looking solution for local food production.

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